

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY FOR DESIGN OF HIGH FUNCTIONAL COMPLEXITY CLOTHING

Fausto Alonso Zuleta Montoya*, Ángela María Echeverri Jaramillo, Blanca Lucia Echavarría Bustamante
 Facultad de Diseño de Vestuario
 Escuela de Arquitectura y Diseño
 Universidad Pontificia Bolivariana
 ✉ fausto.zuleta@upb.edu.co*

ABSTRACT

Following the purposes of the Clothing Design program, which emphasize research processes that explore clothing from different areas, from the materials to production, the project is presented within the field of the exploration of clothing as mediator between the body (acknowledging it as an internal system) and its special context (as an external system). Both systems demand specific and ascertainable requirements that have been determined through research and that will answer through high complexity clothing developed for a specific sport, in this particular case artistic and rhythmic gymnastics.

KEYWORDS: *Clothing design, movement analysis, gymnastics clothing.*

INTRODUCTION

The Universidad Pontificia Bolivariana's Clothing Design Faculty and the Fundación Universitaria María Cano Movement Analysis Laboratory (both located in Medellín) combined academic resources that would allow the development of research projects within social and business sectors. The project "Design and Construction of High Functional Complexity Clothing (technical proposal and construction of new clothes for high performance in sports)" was executed in 2013, with the purpose of making clothes that meet specific sports requirements, in this case rhythmic and artistic gymnastics. This project has been developed in two phases involving technical progress in sports and social areas that become smart solutions for developing high functional clothing. The first phase involved the research method that resulted in the design of sports clothes. The second phase, aimed to develop an analysis of the clothes and the athlete. This article presents the results of the research that are relevant to the Clothing Design and Textiles Research Group (GIDVT) of the Universidad Pontificia Bolivariana.

CONCEPTS

In order to understand the intention of a research project that combines the development of the so-called "high complexity" clothes and the analysis of clothes within the field

of ergonomics science, it is enough to observe the requirements of the case study. These requirements involve the user, the context in which he operates and the clothing product transversally. The difference with other fashion or clothing research projects is that the result is not an adaptive and commercially productive creation but instead it seeks to harbor the most determining solution for a specific need of the case study. This is called high complexity clothing because it interacts with the user's needs within an activity in a demanding context and is not seeking to be commercially viable, since the solution, the activity and the context are what determine the productive aspects of the aforementioned clothing.

High complexity clothing:

"High complexity clothing" refers to clothing development that seeks functional and technical solutions and that within its pattern design does not obey any commercial productive system (Zapata, 2013). Within this concept, the term "technical" fabric for sportswear appears but it can be combined with different functional variables. In order to better understand the term high complexity clothing, we need to relate the products of various brands in the sports industry and the laboratories used in the study and testing of the best possible clothing. These brands undertake much research and development for sports shoes, jerseys, sweatshirts, jackets and accessories for different sports. Brands like Nike, Adidas, Speedo and Columbia Sportwear have their research laboratories, in partnership with universities, technology

centers or industries, to develop highly complex clothing for universal sports such as football, basketball, tennis, golf and swimming among others (Sherman, 2011). High performance military uniforms are another example of this. The purpose of these technical fabrics is to produce high complexity clothing to stimulate the evaporation of perspiration during or after sports in a moderately hot environment. In many cases, these clothes do not provide any thermo regulating, physiological or comfort advantage when compared to traditional cotton clothes, as they have not been made using new technological materials (with memory of form, antibacterial, thermoregulation, etc.) However, a good proposal for anatomic, anthropometric, composition and function response for using clothing made with so-called technological fabrics may benefit and control the physical conditions of the user. This is why techniques for pattern design and the laboratories set up to determine multiple variables are vital in the development and fabrication of clothes intended to help the final performance of the clothing (Fernández, 2013). A research study undertaken at the University of Indiana demonstrated the different implications for high complexity clothing (Med Sci Sports Exerc 2001 Dec 33(12), pp2124-2130). High complexity clothing is not only specified in technological fabrics but also in the important physiological variables and its anthropometrical constructive connotations. Practicing their sport, raises athletes' body temperature (e.g. Skin temperature, central temperature, and heart rate and sweat loss). These variables, together with biochemical analyses and laboratories are used for the design and construction of the clothing. Thus, it is called "high complexity clothing" as it includes all the factors for optimum and comfortable design (Bartels, 2005).

Thermoregulatory Clothing:

One of the best characteristics of high complexity clothing is thermoregulation as this is a determining factor for the good or bad condition of the user in the context in which he is performing. Using sportswear for high competition as a reference point, a correlation between the confection cluster, design and textile industry can be established. The latter, the textile industry, has slowly reacted to the big opportunities that micro-encapsulation has to offer, defining it as the inclusion of materials using very small matrices to be liberated later and gradually (Villena, 2009). Currently, the number of phase change material (PCM) commercial applications in the textile industry continues to grow to give new properties and added value to the final products, such as: medical fabrics or technical fabrics for sports.

Clothes with micro-encapsulation can improve a person's level of thermic comfort because they can solve the heat exchange between the human body and its surroundings (Shelton, 2009). Unexpected temperature surges in the environment or human body as happens with athletes (because of muscular cooling, fever, hormonal changes or organ heating), lead to a thermal imbalance between the body and its surroundings, generating a feeling of discomfort.

Clothes capable of absorbing or emitting heat to the body according to external stimuli may help rapid thermoregulation and a sense of wellbeing, they may also help with energy recovery or controlled energy release, which is known as thermoregulatory clothing.

METHODOLOGY

The project's first phase involved a systematic search by teachers and students approaching an exploration for a monograph. The search explored sport norms, regulations, state of art and timelines, as a research approach indicated by Dorst (2001, 2008) and Jones (1970). In these methods, the approach is based on the collection of theoretical information, which can put together solid project requirements (route 1). A parallel fieldwork project was organized in order to gain knowledge about the sport and the athlete. This research project was ethnographic and brought to the research process closer to the user-context reality (route 2). The case study was divided taking into account the user categories that were established by the context: rhythmic and artistic category, open and women categories and infant, junior and masters categories. In this fieldwork, determining the application approach to the environment to be treated, the biomechanics fundamentals and the clothes that work as prosthesis for the improvement of the activity. These studies merge with the response of textile bases that make up the suit to develop and offer several aids to improve development (Adequacy Filters for route 1 & 2). In the case of suits as prosthesis, this union compliments the development of a simple activity (lift up, walk, grab, and support, among others); however, there is too much to be developed in this field and the research analysis and results can be taken to a more efficient level, when talking about clothing (Shishoo, 2005). This entire methodological framework can be seen in Figure 1.

With this process, we can see that the methodology has a theoretical and explorative approach, according to the scope that is used today in research. These investigative approaches of the project are based on high complexity costume design and provide the basis for the early stages of product development. It is noteworthy that the methodology has come to be completed in stage I, which is determined using research tools for the project, but has not been validated. We are now in Phase II, where the validation and review of laboratory project (FUMC) is undertaken for performance.

The first part allows us to find that the technical basis and the high complexity related to the type of stroke and cuts that have been taken into account to build these types of suits, such as the confection techniques, are far from being the best possible solution for functional high complexity clothing, that's why we built different prototypes and tests in the first phase of the research process. Researchers determined the strains of functional sportswear (Hamill, 2003) (Scott, 2005) (Shishoo, 2005) with which they proved their point that designing the functional high complex suit as a simple creative

Fig. 1. Research process methodology applied to product development

and aesthetic exercise is not enough, it also has to involve responding to a profound knowledge of anatomy, anthropometry, composition and functional response of the technological fabrics, sports physics, and in some special cases design pattern techniques and the use of the laboratory to detect multiple variables. All of this showed the relevance and reach of this research project, and helped in the process and physical activity research phase, which provided the scope for the clothing project. The needs for the development of the clothing were investigated with a theory of applied research, a conceptualization theory, a production theory and a development workshop (Lipovetsky, 1990) (Lurie, 1994) (Vilsser, 2009). It is important to establish that in the research process, we took into account the stress points of the materials, the internal and external forces in the human body and other requirements driven from the impact of the person in action this is being validated with the FUMC (which is in process, as phase II).

RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

For the development of a high complexity clothing project, any analysis between the user-context-product must be a matter for investigation, as must the particularity of each aspect, individually and as a set. The final objectives of the suit are determined by this analysis and are materialized when they are transferred to the business and social environment. All of this resulted in the creation of various designs that focused on the user and analysis category detailed in the case study (See example in figure 2).

The search for the maximum comfort for those users in their contexts arises as the physical and technological challenge

Figure 2. Clothing artistic gymnasts category, male-older. Paths of muscular work: Ricardo Zapata. Photo: Esteban Gutierrez. Gymnast: William Calle (UPB copyright).

for specific high performance activities. This has led to these types of suits becoming more efficient and allowing athletes a better performance, which, in turn, is becoming an important focal point for further research.

In the first phase of the project, the intentions were directed towards the gymnastics field and to competitive purposes. A research process has been developed that involves different actors in highly competitive gymnastics (athletes, national leagues, physiotherapist, sports physiologists and biomedical engineers) in accordance to the possibilities or advice necessary for the development of high performance clothing. In this activity, we proposed the biomechanical analysis to help the material formalization of new suits that grant bigger benefits in their use. The investigation perspective involves social and technological aspects, understanding these fields within movement analysis and the development of new functional high complexity clothing that may aid the improvement of specific activities in different sports.

REFERENCES

- Adanur, S. (1995). *Wellington Sears Handbook of Industrial Textiles*. Pittsburg. Ed. Wellington Sears Company, 1st Edition.
- Adidas Inc. Adidas Research Lab (2012). <http://www.adidas-group.com/en/group/history/> accessed 12 April 2013.
- Bartels, V. T. (2005). *Physiological comfort of sportswear*. In Shhisoo R. *Textiles in Sports*, Cambridge, Woodhead, pp 177-203.
- Dorst, K., Cross N. (2001). *Creativity in the design process: co-evolution of problem-solution*. In *Design Studies*. Vol. 22 (5). pp 425-437.
- Dorst, K. (2008). *Design research- a revolution-waiting-to-happen*. In *Design Studies*. Vol 29. pp 4-11.
- Fernandez, C. (2013). *La profundidad de la apariencia: el vestido en el debate entre el arte y el diseño*. *Poliantea IX* (16). 129-150.
- Benno M. (2010). *Biomechanics of Sports Shoes*. *Journal of Biomechanics*. Vol 44. pp 2522-2523.
- Jones, J. C. (1970). *Design Methods*. New York. Ed. John Willey and Sons.
- Lipovetsky, G. (1990). *L'Empire de l'éphémère : la mode et son destin dans les sociétés modernes*. Barcelona. Ed Anagrama; Col. Argumentos (Spanish versión).
- Lurie, A. (1994). *El Lenguaje de la Moda; Una interpretación de las formas de vestir*. Buenos Aires. Ed. Paidós Contextos.
- Nike Inc. (2012). *Nike Sport Research Lab* "<http://nikeinc.com/news/nike-sport-research-lab-incubates-innovation>" accessed 12 April 2013.
- Shelton, C. L., Raistrick, C., Warburton, K., Siddiqui, K. H. (2009). *Can changes in clinical attire reduce likelihood of cross-infection without jeopardising the doctor-patient relationship?*. In *Journal Hospital Infection*. Vol. 74. pp 22-29.
- Sherman, L. (2011). *The Science of Design, on the cutting edge of functional apparel for health, comfort and sustainability*. In *Terra Issue*. <http://oregonstate.edu/terra/2011/10/the-science-of-design/> accessed 15 April 2013.
- Shisoo, R. (2005). *Textiles in Sport*. Cambridge. Ed. Woodhead Publishing Limited.
- Scott, R. (2005). *Textiles for Protection*. Cambridge. Ed. Woodhead Publishing Limited.
- Villena, M., Morales, H., Lara, G., Martinez R. (2009). *Técnicas de microencapsulación: una propuesta para microencapsular probióticos*. In *Ars Pharmaceutica*. Vol 50 (1). 43-50.
- Vilsser, W.(2009). *Design. One, but in different forms*. In *Design Studies*. Vol 30. pp 187-223.
- Zapata, R., Zuleta, F., & Legarda, F. (2013). *Metodología de construcción de diseño de vestuario de alta complejidad*. In *Experiencias Investigativas del Vestir y la Moda*. Medellín. Ed. UPB. pp 97-106.